

Herbicide use and occurrence of *Echinochloa* spp. in ricefields in dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka

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This ricefield weed survey included 251 fields in the dry and intermediate rice growing zones of Sri Lanka in 1994 and 1995. All species within 5- × 5-m plots were identified and farmers interviewed about practices. During the 1994 maha season (northeastern monsoon, October-December), we identified 132 different weeds belonging to 32 families in 176 fields. During the 1995 yala season (southwestern monsoon, April-August), 96 different weeds belonging to 21 different families were identified in 75 fields. In both seasons, *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link and *E. crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv. (Poaceae) ranked among the 10 most important weed

Table 1. Frequency of *Echinochloa* spp. during the 1994-95 survey in the dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka.

Weed	Frequency (%)	
	Maha season	Yala season
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	52.3	81.3
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	36.9	57.3
<i>Echinochloa frumentacea</i> Link	13.1	21.3
<i>Echinochloa stagnina</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv.	6.8	13.3

species, while *E. frumentacea* Link and *E. stagnina* (Retz.) P. Beauv. occurred less frequently. Overall, *Echinochloa* spp. frequencies were higher during the dry yala season (Table 1). The reason for this might be that during the yala season all cultivated rice is irrigated whereas during the rainy season (maha) upland rice is also grown. Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA), often used in ecological vegetation science, conducted on species occurring in more than three fields, revealed that during maha, *E. crus-galli*

is a typical species in frequently irrigated ricefields, whereas *E. colona* occurs as well under drier regimes. Water level in ricefields during yala, however, does not seem to have a significant influence on their distribution.

From interviews with the farmers, it became clear that the range of herbicides used is very limited. Propanil, active against several grassy and broadleaf weeds, and MCPA, against broadleaves, are the most frequently applied herbicides. Only about a third of the farmers reported using the recommended amounts of herbicides (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Herbicide use (% of farmers interviewed) in ricefields during the 1994-95 survey in the dry and intermediate zones of Sri Lanka.

Class ^a	Propanil	MCPA
I	41.7	37.5
II	20.8	30.6
III	37.5	31.9

^a Class I: no application; class II: amount of herbicide applied is less than recommended; class III: recommended amounts according to the Department of Agriculture.

Integrated weed management through smother intercrops in rainfed lowland rice

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Among the management options in the first 40-50 d of rainfed lowland rice, smother crops can ensure effective weed control. We evaluated the weed-smothering effect of green manure, including *Crotalaria juncea*, *Vigna sinensis*, *Glycine max*, *Sesbania rostrata*, and *S. aculeata* during 1992 and 1994 at the ARS, Mugad, Karnataka, India.

The crop treatments were combined factorially with either hand weeding (HW) alone at 30 d after rice emergence (DE) or with intercultivation (IC) at 15 DE followed by hand weeding at 40

DE. Weed-free check, weedy check, and farmer's practices were included for comparison (see table). The rice and green manure seeds were mixed in a

100:25 kg ha⁻¹ proportion and sown in 20-cm rows by seed drill in semidry soil at the onset of the monsoon season. Green manures were buried in stand-

Grain yield and weed dry weight in rainfed lowland rice as influenced by integrated weed management involving smother crops. Karnataka, India. 1992 and 1994.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	
	1992	1994	1992	1994
<i>C. juncea</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.2	5.9	175	78
<i>C. juncea</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.2	6.1	50	49
<i>V. sinensis</i> + HW at 30 DE	6.3	5.8	103	89
<i>V. sinensis</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.7	6.8	25	49
<i>G. max</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.3	5.9	58	137
<i>G. max</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.9	7.2	45	69
<i>S. rostrata</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.9	5.8	106	90
<i>S. rostrata</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.1	5.9	53	53
<i>S. aculeata</i> + HW at 30 DE	5.3	4.6	181	124
<i>S. aculeata</i> + IC at 15 DE + HW at 40 DE	6.7	5.2	36	100
Weed-free check	6.6	6.6	111	8
Weedy check	3.2	2.7	361	461
Farmer's practice	6.8	6.7	81	40
Butachlor + HW at 30 DE	6.5	6.7	95	49
LSD (0.05)	1	1.2		42

^aHW = hand weeding; DE = days after rice emergence; IC = intercultivation.